

ESSENTIAL OIL FROM THE LEAVES OF *ATALANTIA MONOPHYLLA*
(D.C. PRODR, FLOURBINDAWIGHT), WILD LIME OIL

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The essential oil (0.4-0.6% on dry leaves) from the leaves of *Atalantia monophylla* comprises l-sabinene (38%), l-linalol (14%), l-linalyl acetate (17%) and unidentified higher terpene esters (29%) belonging to azulene group. Physical and chemical constants of the oil have been determined.

Atalantia monophylla, a shrub or treelet about 6 metres tall with short sharp spines belongs to the Rutaceae family. It is distributed throughout S. India. The oil under investigation was obtained from the leaves collected from the Hosur Cattle Farm, near Bangalore.

The berries of the *Atalantia monophylla* yield a warm oil which is in native medicine considered as valuable in chronic rheumatism and paralysis (Ainslie: cf. Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. I, pp. 481-82). In the Konkan the leaf juice is an ingredient in a compound liniment used in hemiplegia. In Ceylon the fresh leaves are bruised, mixed with salt and heated, and then applied to the part bitten by a snake (Roberts: cf. Kirtikar and Basu, *loc. cit.*).

Steam-distillation of the Oil from the Leaves.—A total of 600 lbs. leaves of *Atalantia monophylla* was distilled in steam under different conditions and the yield of the oil and its characteristics were examined (cf. Chobe and Rao, *Proc. Soc. Biol. Chem. India* 1937, 2, 16). The yield of the oil varied from 0.4 to 0.6% on the dry leaves. An appreciably smaller yield was obtained after drying, indicating a loss of the oil during drying. The ratios of the oil to steam, when blowing through the raw material, were 0.0094 and 0.22 respectively.

The oil is brown in colour with a pleasant citrus odour, very similar to the oil from the carpels of *xanthoxylum badrunga*, which is a popular flavouring material in Mysore and S. India. With superheated steam up to 160°, a quantity of the oil coming out per unit area of steam was double that at 100° for every 10° rise in temperature. Distillation in steam at 100 mm. gave a low ratio of 0.15.

The essential oil from the leaves of *Atalantia monophylla* had not been examined in detail by any of the previous workers, though the oil was obtained for the first time by Chobe and Rao (*loc. cit.*) who examined the oil just for its analytical constants. Besides comparing its analytical constants with that observed by those workers, the oil has now been examined in detail and its chemical constituents have been isolated and characterised. A comparative values of the analytical constants of the oil are given below.

	As observed by the authors.	By Chobe and Rao.
1. Density at 30°	0.8675	0.8561
2. Refractive index	1.4650 at 31.5°.	1.4600 at 30°
3. Optical rotation	-34.18° at 28°	-33.2° at 30°
4. Sapon. value	92.85	79.3
5. Do after acetylation	139.3	113.5
6. Acid value	6.85	0.8

The oil soluble in one volume of 90% alcohol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fractionation of the Oil under reduced pressure.—The oil (285 g.) was fractionated under reduced pressure using a Vigreux column of about 21 inches long and the following fractions were collected and their analytical constants noted.

TABLE I

Fractions.	Yield.	d_{40}^{20} .	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.	n_D^{25} .	Sap. value.	Sap. value (after acetylation.)	Acid value.	Colour.
I. 48°-60°/3-4 mm.	110 g. (38.6%)	0.84805	-67°.59 (10% soln. in CHCl ₃)	1.4518	10.18	19.5	2.4	Colorless
II. 70°-85°/3-4	93 g. (33%)	0.89540	-18°.7	1.4541	154.5	240.8	3.1	Do
III. 100°-115°/3-4	15 g.	0.93920	-4°.95	1.4680	136.1	145.6	15.7	Yellowish
IV. 125°-130°/3-4	11	0.96550	-0°.97	1.4773	109.2	131.4	18.9	Do
V. 140°-150°/0.05	3	0.9780	+2°.587	1.4786	114.5	—	—	Reddish brown
VI. 175°-178°/0.05	5.6	0.9787	-14°.33	1.4801	110.9	—	—	Do
VII. 180°-190°/0.05	6.6	0.9801	+2°.123	1.4876	141.3	—	—	Do

It is quite clear from the analytical constants that fraction I consists mainly of hydrocarbons and fraction II, mainly of esters and alcohols. Further, it was observed that after distilling off the fractions I-IV the higher boiling fractions were either polymerising or decomposing. Hence, attention was drawn, mainly towards fractions I and II and to determining its chemical constituents.

Refractionation of Fraction I (48°-60°/3-4 mm.).—The hydrocarbon fraction (48°-60°/3-4 mm.) was then fractionated carefully under reduced pressure of 8 mm. and three fractions were collected and their analytical constants were determined as in Table II.

TABLE II

Fractions.	yield.	d_{40}^{20} .	$[\beta]_D^{25}$.	n_D^{25} .	Sapon value.	Sapon value after acetylation.
1. 50°-52°/8 mm.	18.1 g.	0.84245	-50°.10	1.4608	23.22	—
2. 52°-54°/8	72	0.84675	-54°.66	1.4636	3.67	6.56
3. 56°-59°/8	8.4	0.84847	-44°.24	1.4655	5.8	—

The optical rotations of the fractions 1, 2 and 3 in Table II were also noted with 20% solutions in chloroform and they were calculated as $-94^{\circ}.5$, $-98^{\circ}.62$ and $-77^{\circ}.49$ respectively.

The fraction $52^{\circ}\text{-}54^{\circ}/8$ mm. was again fractionated over metallic sodium at atmospheric pressure and was collected at $158^{\circ}\text{-}159.5^{\circ}/685$ mm. This had the following analytical constants: $d_{4}^{20} = 0.8417$; $n_D^{20} = 1.4647$; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -58^{\circ}.06$ and -112° (with 20% solution in chloroform).

This fraction gave no nitrosochloride or bromide but with dry HCl gas in ethereal solution gave terpinene dihydrochloride, m.p. 52° . It also gave on oxidation sabenic acid, m.p. 57° . Thus, it was characterised as *l-sabinene* (38% of the oil).

Re fractionation.—The fraction $70^{\circ}\text{-}85^{\circ}/3\text{-}4$ mm. was then fractionated carefully under reduced pressure and was separated into the alcohol and ester fractions.

TABLE III

Fractions	Yield.	d_{4}^{20} .	n_D^{20}	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	Sap. value.	Sap. value after acetyl.
1. $70^{\circ}\text{-}75^{\circ}/2$ mm.	40 g.	0.87049	1.4655	$-18^{\circ}.02$	32.6	223.3
2. $75^{\circ}\text{-}80^{\circ}/2$	48.8	0.90869	1.4520	$-8^{\circ}.59$	232.9	243.4

The fraction $70^{\circ}\text{-}75^{\circ}/2$ mm. was again fractionated and a pure fraction distilling at $72^{\circ}\text{-}73^{\circ}/4\text{-}5$ mm. was collected. This had the following constants.

Boiling point at 685 mm.	... $193\text{-}94^{\circ}$
Specific gravity at 25°	... 0.87091
Ref. index at 26°	... 1.4653
Sapon. value	... 5.92
Sapon. value after acetylation	... 244.3

The alcohol fraction gave with isocyanate, the urethane derivative $C_8H_9NHCO_2C_{10}H_{17}$ (Found: N, 5.21%. Calc. N, 5.12 per cent). m.p. 65° . On oxidation it gave citral. Thus it was characterised as *l-linalol*.

The ester fraction $75^{\circ}\text{-}80^{\circ}/2$ mm. was fractionated and two fractions were collected and their analytical constants noted as follows.

TABLE IV

Fractions.	Yield.	d_{4}^{20} .	n_D^{20} .	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	Sap. value.	Sap. value after acetylation
1. $105^{\circ}\text{-}108^{\circ}/16$ mm	8.2 g.	0.92309	1.4536	$-10^{\circ}.56$	185.8	220.8
2. $108^{\circ}\text{-}110^{\circ}/26$	30.5	0.91149	1.4514	$-9^{\circ}.57$	245.8	245.9

It was clear that the ester fraction $108^{\circ}\text{-}110^{\circ}/16$ mm. was quite pure as the sap. values remained unaltered before and after acetylation. The ester on saponification liberated *l-linalol* which was characterised in a similar manner as above. The acid portion of the ester was then characterised by preparing the silver salt of the organic acid. The aqueous layer after saponification of the ester was acidified with sulphuric

acid and the organic acid steam distilled. The aqueous distillate was neutralised with Na_2CO_3 and concentrated. It was then filtered hot and on cooling, after a few days the sodium salt crystallised. The silver salt was then prepared and this on analysis gave the following results.

- I. 0.4725 g of silver salt gave 0.3024 g. of silver.
- II. 0.4435 g. of silver salt gave 0.2835 g. of silver.
Percentage of silver in I = 64.0
Percentage of Silver in II = 63.93
Percentage of silver in CH_3COOAg = 64.67

Thus the values of the percentage of silver salt prepared agreed nearly with the theoretical value of 64.67. Thus the ester was identified as *l-linalyl acetate*.

These higher terpenes might be belonging to the sesquiterpenes of the azulene group as it was observed that the higher boiling fractions, other than those that were characterised, were observed to be giving deep blue colorations with bromine dissolved in glacial acetic acid.

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